

Passively Induced Contextual Plasticity in Sound Localization in Real and Virtual Environments

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Abstract.

Two experiments examined a localization aftereffect, called contextual plasticity (CP), induced by repeated exposure to transient stimuli presented from a fixed location. The first experiment tested whether passive exposure to the context is sufficient to induce CP in a reverberant classroom. The second experiment tested it in a virtual environment (anechoic or reverberant). Targets (2-ms noise bursts) and adaptors (trains of 12 such bursts) were presented on separate interleaved trials and subjects localized the targets while passively listening to the adaptors. The passively received adaptor caused responses to the targets to be displaced by up to 16° away from the adaptor location. This effect was strongest and fastest in the virtual anechoic environment, while only reaching 5° in real reverberation. Response standard deviations were also affected, increasing in the real environment while having a complex effect in the virtual environments. Finally, Information Transfer Rate was evaluated, showing that target spatial resolvability decreased near the adaptor location in all environments. Overall, these results show that passive listening to the context is sufficient to induce CP. However, the effect is exaggerated in virtual environments, where listeners might modify their localization strategy, using the adaptor as an anchor, which causes additional performance deterioration.

1 I. INTRODUCTION

2 Horizontal sound localization can be influenced by exposure to preceding sounds on multiple
3 time scales. Early studies examining the auditory *localization aftereffects* (LA) showed that prolonged
4 presentation of an “adapting” sound (with duration on the order of seconds) causes the subsequent
5 target sound to shift away from the adaptor location (Flügel, 1920; Thurlow and Jack, 1973). Later
6 studies showed that the effect is present under headphones as well as in the sound field (Canévet
7 and Meunier, 1996; Carlile et al., 2001), for stimuli with various frequency content (Canévet and
8 Meunier, 1996; Laback, 2023; Meunier et al., 2018), and across a range of interstimulus intervals
9 (Kashino and Nishida, 1998). Additionally, several studies examined spatial discriminability effects
10 induced by an adaptor (e.g., Getzmann, 2004; Maddox et al., 2014; Maier et al., 2010). Notably, all
11 these studies used adaptor stimuli that were relatively long, with durations of at least several hundred
12 milliseconds.

13 Kopčo et al. (2007) examined the effect of preceding stimuli on localization of brief 2-ms “click”
14 sounds and found a more complex pattern. On one hand, for brief inter-stimulus intervals (ISIs) up
15 to 100 ms, the *adaptor* click induced an attractive shift in the perceived location of the subsequent
16 target click towards the adaptor location, likely due to mechanisms related to precedence effect and
17 precedence buildup (Brown et al., 2015). On the other hand, the cumulative effect of multiple
18 adaptor presentations was that the targets, when presented alone without any immediately preceding
19 adaptor, shifted away from their reference location, possibly due to the same mechanism that causes
20 the LA. The later phenomenon, called *contextual plasticity* (CP), is likely to be related to the LA as it
21 involves similar shifts away from the adaptor (Andrejková et al., 2023; Hládek et al., 2017; Kopčo et
22 al., 2015).

23 While the LA has been examined for longer stimuli, CP only has been examined for brief clicks,
24 for which it builds up very slowly over the time course of seconds and minutes. Also, many aspects

25 of CP are currently unknown. For example, all the studies in which it has been examined so far used
26 an active listening task on the adaptor trials, not only on the target trials (the subject performed a
27 localization task on the adaptor trials which contained both an adaptor and a target with a brief ISI),
28 and they were performed in real anechoic and reverberant environments.

29 The current study presents two experiments. Experiment 1 examined the role of active listening
30 in CP. Active listening has been shown to be important for many aspects of sound localization
31 (Deouell et al., 2007; Higgins et al., 2017). And, while the previous CP studies used active listening
32 tasks on adaptor trials, the LA studies typically used passive exposure to adaptor stimuli. Therefore,
33 assuming that CP and LA are related, the current Experiment 1 examined whether passive listening
34 to the adaptors is sufficient to induce CP as well.

35 Experiment 1, as well as all the previous CP studies, was performed in a real environment.
36 Virtual environments are becoming more common both in everyday listening and in auditory
37 research (Carlile, 1996). Their limited veridicality, caused by limitations in simulation and
38 reproduction accuracy, can cause differences in performance as well as in the strategies used by the
39 listeners. For example, they can induce biases or increased variability in responses, and listeners
40 might try to rely more on the use of relative cues than absolute cues for sound localization (Kopčo
41 et al., 2010; Recanzone et al., 1998). To evaluate these possibilities, experiment 2 was performed in
42 virtual environment, both reverberant (similar to the real reverberant environment of Experiment 1)
43 and anechoic. It also examined whether the changes in the CP strength, rate of buildup, and
44 response variability change between these environments, as shown for real stimuli (Andrejková et al.,
45 2023; Kopco et al., 2007).

46 The mechanisms of CP and LA are not well understood, even though several studies proposed
47 models of different aspects of LA (Carlile et al., 2001; Dingle et al., 2012; Laback, 2023; Lingner et
48 al., 2018). Traditionally, it has been assumed that the LA adaptation is a result of a local suppression

49 or “fatiguing” in the spatial channels near the adaptor (Carlile et al., 2001; Dingle et al., 2012),
50 resulting in response biases away from the adaptor location and decreased discriminability of sources
51 near the adaptor. Lingner et al. (2018) proposed an alternative model that suggests that the effect of
52 adaptor is to increase spatial separability of sources near the adaptor and the biases are a side effect
53 of that benefit. While the current study does not directly measure discriminability, it introduces the
54 Information Transfer Rate (ITR; Nelken and Chechik, 2007) as a related measure based on
55 localization. It compares ITR with response standard deviation (SD) and Pearson correlation
56 coefficient (CC) as localization-based measures related to discriminability to evaluate whether the
57 current data are more consistent with the models of Carlile or Dingle vs. the Lingner model. Finally,
58 current analysis also explores whether CP and LA are more consistent with models that assume
59 spatial auditory processing channels are relatively narrow (Carlile et al., 2001) vs. broad hemispheric
60 (Lingner et al., 2018), or some mixture of the two (Dingle et al., 2012).

61 The main hypotheses explored here are: (1) that CP and LA are at least partially related,
62 predicting that CP will be induced by passive exposure to the adaptor; (2) that CP is influenced not
63 only by bottom-up adaptation in spatial representation but also by top-down factors—such as
64 subjects employing different response strategies (absolute vs. relative) in different environments—
65 predicting that the magnitude of CP effects will vary across environments; and (3) that the neural
66 representation underlying CP consists of relatively narrow processing channels, predicting that CP
67 effects will align with the Carlile et al. (2001) model.

68 II. METHODS

69 The data described here were collected in two experiments. Experiment 1 was done in real
70 reverberant and experiment 2 in virtual anechoic and reverberant environment. Setup, stimuli, and
71 procedures were similar to the previous CP studies (Hládek et al., 2017; Kopčo et al., 2007, 2015).

72 **A. Subjects**

73 Eight subjects (three females), with ages ranging from 19 to 28 years, participated in Experiment
74 1. Ten different subjects (five female), nine with ages ranging from 19 to 29 years plus one 70 years
75 old, participated in experiment 2. All subjects, except for the 70-year-old one, had normal hearing as
76 confirmed by audiometric screening (all thresholds within 15 dB hearing level) and gave informed
77 consent as approved by the of P. J. Šafárik University's Ethics Committee (the 70-year-old subject's
78 thresholds ranged from 15 to 65 dB HL, with higher thresholds at higher frequencies; the subject
79 was not excluded since the hearing loss was primarily in the high-frequency region not critical for
80 horizontal sound localization, and since the subject's data were not identified as outliers). One
81 subject from experiment 2 was excluded due to not following instructions. For three other subjects,
82 data from one whole session of experiment 2 were excluded, identified as outliers based on
83 anomalous baseline performance (importantly, as a session included all combinations of conditions,
84 this exclusion influenced data for all conditions equally).

85 **B. Setup and listening environment**

86 Both experiments were performed in a quiet darkened midsize reverberant room (5.5 x 4.7 x 2.8
87 m; broadband $T_{60} = 1.1$ s) using identical stimuli and similar setup. Eleven loudspeakers were placed
88 in a semicircle with a radius of 1.2 m at azimuths spanning -45° to $+45^\circ$ (step of 11.25°) and two at
89 $\pm 90^\circ$ (Fig. 1A), approximately at the level of the subjects' ears. The speakers were covered with a
90 dark acoustically transparent fabric so the subjects could not see their locations. Subjects were seated
91 on a chair at the center of the semicircle, facing the middle speaker, with their heads supported by a
92 headrest. A Polhemus Liberty position tracker was used to monitor the subject's head position and
93 orientation.

94 A custom-made system consisting of a silent projector (Mitsubishi PK10), a 20 x 250 cm
95 projector screen attached above the loudspeakers spanning the azimuths of $\pm 60^\circ$, and a numeric

96 keypad was used to collect the subject's responses. The projector provided instructions to the
97 subject. During the trials, a unique 2-character combination (consisting of decimal digits and
98 symbols “*”, “-“, “+”, and “/”) was shown at each azimuth from -59° to 59° in 1° steps (the 2-
99 character combinations were randomly permuted on each trial). The subject responded by entering
100 on the numeric keyboard the character pair nearest to the perceived stimulus location and pressing
101 Enter. On the adaptor trials, the subject responded by only pressing Enter, i.e., without any
102 engagement in active localization. This system was previously shown to provide the most accurate
103 measurements of the subjects' responses when compared to the hand-held pointing response
104 method (Kopčo et al., 2015). During a training session at the beginning of the experiment, the
105 subjects practiced responding using this method until they were comfortable doing it without
106 looking at the keypad.

107 A personal computer, placed outside the experimental room, controlled the experiments using
108 custom-written MATLAB code. Experiment 1 used the loudspeakers in the experimental room (Fig.
109 1A), 5 to present adaptors (locations: 0° ; $\pm 45^\circ$; $\pm 90^\circ$) and 6 to present targets (locations: $\pm 11.25^\circ$;
110 $\pm 22.5^\circ$; $\pm 33.75^\circ$). Experiment 2 used virtual stimuli while the subjects sat in the same experimental
111 room (Fig. 1B), with 3 simulated locations to present adaptors (0° ; $\pm 50^\circ$) and 6 simulated locations
112 to present targets ($\pm 10^\circ$; $\pm 20^\circ$; $\pm 30^\circ$). The 90° adaptor was omitted from experiment 2 to make its
113 duration comparable to experiment 1 while using two different virtual environments.

114 C. Stimuli and procedure

115 Two types of stimuli were used (Fig. 1C). The target (T) was a 2-ms frozen broad-band white
116 noise burst (a “click”), as used in the previous CP studies. The adaptor (A) was a train of 12 such
117 identical clicks presented at the rate of 10 Hz ($T = 100$ ms). Note that the total duration of the
118 target and adaptor stimuli (as well as the silent adaptor used in the baseline) was fixed for each
119 stimulus presentation. Thus, the target stimulus was zero-padded prior to the click onset. The stimuli

120 were presented at the level of 64 dBA (peak RMS value, measured using a long version of the
121 stimulus) in experiment 1 and at a perceptually matched loudness in experiment 2 (achieved by
122 adjusting the virtual reverberant stimulus level while listening to interleaved real and virtual stimuli
123 by the authors). The experiment 2 stimuli were presented in a virtual environment created using a
124 single set of non-individualized binaural room impulse responses (BRIR) measured in a similar room
125 on a subject that did not participate in this study, using procedures and devices that were, unless
126 specified otherwise, identical to previous studies (Kopčo et al., 2012; Shinn-Cunningham et al.,
127 2005). The reverberant room simulations used the whole BRIRs, while the anechoic ones used a
128 pseudo-anechoic HRTF obtained by windowing the corresponding BRIR prior to the first
129 reflection. The stimuli were generated using a digital-to-analog converter (RME Fireface UFX),
130 amplified (Knoll MX1255) and sent to loudspeakers (Canton Plus X3) in experiment 1 or sent to
131 headphones (Sennheiser HD 800) in experiment 2.

132 Each experiment contained 3 sessions, each performed on a different day. A session consisted of
133 runs, one run for each fixed adaptor position (including a no-adaptor baseline), resulting in six runs
134 in experiment 1 and eight runs in experiment 2 (four each for the anechoic and reverberant
135 environments). The experimental runs consisted of three parts: pre-adaptation (12 trials, target
136 stimuli only), adaptation (168 trials – adaptors and targets randomly interleaved with equal
137 probability), and post-adaptation (18 trials, target stimuli only). The target presentation order was
138 pseudo-random such that each target was presented at least once before any target was presented for
139 a second time etc. Thus, runs could be sub-divided into subruns corresponding to groups of trials in
140 which each target was presented exactly once. The baseline runs were identical to the adaptor runs
141 except that the adaptor was replaced by silence. The experiment was self-paced, with average trial
142 duration of approximately 4 seconds, including stimulus presentation, response, and a 0.5-second
143 pause before the next trial. One run lasted approximately 11-12 minutes. After each run the subjects

144 could take a break. With the breaks, one session took approximately 2 hours in experiment 1 and 2.5
145 hours in experiment 2.

146
147 FIG. 1. Experimental setup and stimuli. A) Setup of the real reverberant environment used in
148 experiment 1. B) Setup of the simulated sources used in the virtual anechoic and reverberant
149 environments in experiment 2. White speakers represent targets. Colored speakers represent
150 adaptors, each color corresponding to one adaptor location (results in the following figures use the
151 same color code to represent different adaptor locations). C) Stimuli used in the experiments. The
152 target stimulus was a 2-ms click. Adaptor was a train of 12 such identical clicks.

153 **D. Analysis**

154 All subject responses were recorded as discrete angles from -59° to 59° . Outliers were removed
155 from the adaptation part (subruns 3—16) of each run, separately for each subject and target angle.
156 An outlier was defined as a response with absolute value deviating by more than 4 times the median
157 absolute deviation re. the median response in a given run (Leys et al., 2013). Around 2% of the
158 experiment 1 data and 5% of the experiment 2 data were excluded. Response biases were computed
159 as an average across the whole adaptation part of each run, while the response standard deviations
160 (SDs) only considered the final 10 subruns (subruns 7-16) of each run when the responses reached a
161 stable state.

162 All reported statistical analyses were performed as multi-way repeated measures or mixed
163 analyses of variance (ANOVAs), using CLEAVE software (Herron, 2005). The reported statistical
164 values were corrected for potential violations of sphericity using the Greenhouse–Geisser epsilon.
165 All t-tests were two-tailed and used Bonferroni correction (unless specified otherwise). The
166 significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$ was used in all tests.

167 Two overall performance measures were considered, Pearson’s correlation coefficient r and the
168 Information Transfer Rate (Nelken and Chechik, 2007; Sagi and Svirski, 2008). The r represents the
169 extent to which the responses are linearly related to the actual target locations, while the ITR is a
170 measure of how much information about the actual target location can be extracted by observing the
171 responses, and it does not assume a linear relationship. For both measures, the responses for targets
172 from one hemisphere (e.g., $+10^\circ$, $+20^\circ$, and $+30^\circ$) of the final 10 subruns in a run were considered to
173 compute the value. To compute the ITR, the procedures of Vlahou et al. (2021) were applied, with
174 bin size of 1° used to estimate the probability distributions. Specifically, we defined $ITR =$
175 $H(X; Y)/H(X)$, where $H(X; Y) = \sum_{x,y} p(x,y) \log (p(x,y)/p(x)p(y))$, $H(X) =$
176 $-\sum_x p(x) \log (p(x))$. Variable $p(x)$ is the probability of occurrence of stimulus x , $p(y)$ is the

177 probability of occurrence of response y , and $p(x, y)$ is the probability of the joint occurrence of x
178 and y (Miller and Nicely, 1955).

179 **III. RESULTS**

180 Results from both experiments are presented in parallel to allow a direct comparison of the
181 effects in real vs. virtual environments. First, we analyze the effects of adaptor on response biases
182 and SDs for data averaged across time. Then, overall performance is assessed using ITR and
183 correlation measures to evaluate the data against two alternative models of auditory spatial
184 adaptation. Finally, we examine the temporal profile of the buildup of contextual bias on data
185 averaged across target locations.

186 **A. Response Bias**

187 The upper panels of Fig. 2 show the across-subject mean response location as a function of
188 target location, separately for the different adaptor conditions (5 or 3 adaptor locations + no
189 adaptor; encoded by color) and the two experiments (panel A for the real-room experiment 1; panels
190 B and C, respectively, for the virtual reverberant and anechoic environments of experiment 2).
191 Overall, the responses are fairly accurate in all conditions (all lines are near the diagonal).
192 Considering the no-adaptor baseline, there is a slight underestimation of the response azimuths in
193 the real environment and an overestimation in the virtual environments (black line shows bias
194 towards the midline in panel A and away from the midline in panels B and C). The individual
195 adaptors caused consistent effects with respect to the baseline in all environments. For example, the
196 adaptors on the left induced a rightward bias (blue and cyan lines fall above the black lines), while
197 the adaptors on the right induced a leftward bias (red and magenta lines fall below the black lines).
198 Also, all the graphs are largely left-right symmetrical (blue lines are above the black lines mostly on
199 the left, while the red lines are below the black lines mostly on the right).

200 To focus on the effects of adaptors, the data are replotted in the lower row of Fig. 2 such that
201 each lower panel shows the same data as the corresponding upper panel after subtracting out the
202 baseline and after combining the left-right symmetrical conditions (e.g., the blue point at -33° in
203 each lower panel was obtained by averaging the -33° blue point and the negative of the $+33^\circ$ red
204 point from the corresponding upper panel). Thus, in the lower panels, the graphs in the left-hand
205 portion (locations -33° to -11°) are identical to those in the right-hand portion (locations $+11^\circ$ to
206 $+33^\circ$) after a rotation about the origin and a swapping of the red/magenta and blue/cyan colors; the
207 green lines, corresponding to the 0° adaptor, are themselves symmetric about the origin). To stress
208 this symmetry, the right-hand half of each graph is shown using a thick line, while the left-hand half
209 is shown using a thin line. (Note that, analogically, the data above and below the x-axis are reflected
210 and flipped copies of each other. For example, the red line is obtained by rotating the blue line
211 around the origin). Therefore, the description below only considers the red, magenta, and green data
212 to describe different effects.

213 In experiment 1 (Fig. 2A), repulsion away from the adaptor was observed in most conditions,
214 with maxima ranging from $4-5^\circ$ for the lateral adaptors (magenta and red lines at 33°) to 3° for the
215 frontal adaptor (green line at 33°). For the lateral adaptors, the bias decreased for targets further
216 away from the adaptor (red and magenta lines increase from right to left) while for the frontal
217 adaptor the effect grew with distance from the adaptor or stayed stable (green line grows from left
218 to right). Finally, the two lateral adaptors had similar but slightly different effects, with the 90°
219 adaptor causing a stronger repulsion for the nearby targets (magenta is below red at 33°) while the
220 45° adaptor caused a stronger repulsion for the contralateral targets (red is below magenta at -11° to
221 -33°). These results were confirmed by ANOVA with the factors of target location (11° , 22° , 33°)
222 and adaptor location (-90° , -45° , 0° , 45° , 90°) which found a significant main effect of adaptor ($F(4,$
223 $28)=57.3$, $p<0.001$), target ($F(2, 14)=11.30$, $p=0.001$), as well as their interaction ($F(8, 56)=9.25$,

224 $p < 0.001$). A follow-up partial ANOVA performed on the frontal-adaptor data found a significant
 225 effect of target ($F(2, 14) = 8.1$; $p < 0.005$) and a partial ANOVA performed on the lateral adaptor data
 226 with the factors of adaptor ($90^\circ, 45^\circ$) and target ($-33^\circ, -22^\circ, -11^\circ, 11^\circ, 22^\circ, 33^\circ$) found a significant
 227 interaction between the factors adaptor x target ($F(5, 35) = 4.74$; $p = 0.0021$) as well as significant main
 228 effect of target ($F(5, 35) = 20.44$; $p < 0.001$), confirming that the effects of the two lateral adaptors
 229 were slightly but significantly different.

230
 231 FIG. 2 Upper panels show a mean response (\pm SEM) in target trials in experiment 1 (panel A) and
 232 experiment 2 (panels B and C), plotted as a function of target location separately for each adaptor
 233 condition (including no-adaptor baseline). For each panel in the upper row, a panel in the lower row
 234 shows the bias (\pm SEM) in responses of each adaptor re. no-adaptor baseline after mirroring the
 235 data, assuming the effects are left-right symmetric. Thick lines highlight the subset of data points
 236 that are independent after the mirroring.

237 In experiment 2 (Figs. 2B and 2C), the central adaptor effects were similar to those of
238 experiment 1 (compare the green lines across all three panels), while the lateral adaptor effects were
239 much stronger, in particular in the virtual anechoic environment (red line in panel C reaches -16° ,
240 while it reaches around -12° in panel B). These results were confirmed by ANOVA performed on
241 the biases with factors of target (10° , 20° , 30°), adaptor (-50° , 0° , 50°) and environment (reverberant
242 and anechoic) which found significant main effects of the factors adaptor ($F(2,16)=146.43$,
243 $p<0.001$), environment ($F(1,8)=6.13$, $p=0.038$), and target ($F(2,16)=3.73$, $p=0.0003$), as well as a
244 significant adaptor x target interaction ($F(4,32)=7.22$, $p=0.002$).

245 *1. Discussion*

246 The results of experiment 1 confirm the hypothesis that engagement in active localization task is
247 not required to induce CP. The bias sizes induced here by a 12-click adaptor in a passive listening
248 condition (3° - 5°), however, are smaller than those induced in previous studies by an 8-click adaptor
249 in similar setups using active listening (9° - 10° ; Andrejková et al., 2023; Hládek et al., 2017). It is
250 possible that engagement in active localization performance on the contextual trials also contributes
251 to CP. Importantly, the setup of the previous studies differed from the current study also in other
252 ways, not only in the active contextual localization task. Given these differences, it is impossible to
253 use these comparisons to draw a conclusion about how large, if any, the contribution of active
254 listening to CP might be.

255 The two lateral adaptors (45° and 90°) produced a similar, even if statistically different, pattern
256 of biases in experiment 1. This result suggests either 1) that the adaptor effects are hemisphere-
257 specific but approximately independent of the specific adaptor location for lateral adaptors (Kopco
258 et al., 2019; Lingner et al., 2018), or 2) that CP also depends on adaptor laterality, becoming stronger
259 (and more local) as the adaptor moves to the side. The latter alternative suggests that CP actually is
260 stronger for the 90° adaptor because previous studies showed that CP decreases for targets further

261 away from the adaptor (Kopčo et al., 2007) and thus the biases would have been much stronger for
262 targets at 50° to 80° for the 90° adaptor if those locations were included (as shown in Andrejková et
263 al., 2023; Hládek et al., 2017).

264 The frontal adaptor caused a weaker bias than the lateral adaptors, consistent with the
265 suggestion that the effect strength grows with adaptor laterality. However, the effect is much weaker
266 than that observed for a similar setup by Hládek et al. (2017), in which an 8-click frontal adaptor
267 induced a 9° shift when all the targets were located only on one side of the adaptor, at locations
268 from 11° to 79°. So, it is possible that the reduced biases in the current study were caused by the
269 presence of the targets on both sides of the adaptor. This would suggest that CP is determined by
270 the distribution of all stimuli, including both adaptors and targets, not just the adaptors (Andrejková
271 et al., 2023; Laback, 2023). Finally, the notion that CP is not always strongest near the adaptor and
272 decreasing with adaptor-target separation is also supported by the observation that, for the 0°
273 adaptor in the current study, the bias grew, or stayed flat, with increased adaptor-target separation.

274 In the virtual environments of experiment 2, the lateral adaptors induced much larger biases
275 than in the real environment of experiment 1, while the frontal adaptor's effect was comparable
276 across all three environments. We are not aware of any previous CP or LA studies that directly
277 compared the effects in virtual and real environments. Moreover, most of the LA studies were
278 performed in virtual environments and they used arbitrary response scales instead of reporting
279 perceived angle (e.g., Dingle et al., 2012; Laback, 2023; Lingner et al., 2018). It is difficult to
280 determine the main reason why the virtual lateral effects are larger in the current study. One
281 possibility is that the virtual environment does not provide any real-world anchors, resulting in
282 increased uncertainty about the percepts and possible changes in response strategy. For example, the
283 listeners might rely more on relative cue values of the targets referenced to the known locations of
284 the adaptors, while in real environments they use the values of the stimulus acoustic cues to directly

285 estimate the absolute location of the target. Such a switching strategy might only affect the lateral-
286 adaptor performance but not the frontal adaptor performance because the 0° reference is always
287 available. Another option is that the effect might have been caused by the fact that no $\pm 90^\circ$
288 adaptors were used in experiment 2 and so the subjects expanded their response range to cover the
289 whole perceptual space. However, this explanation is unlikely as it predicts that the frontal adaptor
290 responses also become more biased. Also, note that the subjects overestimated the target azimuths
291 also in the no-adaptor baselines of experiment 2, suggesting that they might be biased to use the
292 whole response range even if the stimuli only come from a limited range, or that they again respond
293 relative to the 0° anchor and in general tend to overestimate the differences they perceive.

294 Finally, the lateral adaptors induced larger biases in the virtual anechoic than reverberant
295 environment of experiment 2, consistent with larger CP observed in real anechoic than reverberant
296 space (Andrejková et al., 2023). Since the presence of reverberation results in some reflections
297 coming from all the directions, not only from the directions corresponding to actual adaptor and
298 target locations, the distribution of received stimuli becomes more uniform and thereby, on average,
299 more biased towards the median plane, possibly causing the reduced CP.

300 **B. Response Standard Deviations**

301 Figure 3 presents the response standard deviation (SD) results using a layout identical to Fig. 2.
302 The upper panels show the across-subject mean SD as a function of target location separately for
303 the different adaptor conditions (colors) and experiments (panels). Overall, the SDs vary both across
304 the adaptors and experiments, with the smallest SDs of 3° - 4° observed in the real environment
305 (panel A) and larger SDs of 4° - 7° in the virtual environments (panels B and C). Confirming this, a
306 mixed ANOVA performed only on the baseline data (black lines) of the real reverberant and virtual
307 reverberant environments (panel A vs. panel B) with a within-subject factor of target (6 azimuths)
308 and a between-subject factor of environment (real reverberant vs. virtual reverberant) only found a

309 main effect of environment ($F(1, 15)=18.58, p=0.001$), while a similar ANOVA performed only on
310 the virtual reverberant vs. virtual anechoic data from experiment 2 found no significant difference.

311 The adaptor effects also differ across the panels. Adaptors induced increases in SDs in the real
312 environment (non-black lines tend to be above the black lines in panel A) and a complex pattern of
313 increases and decreases in the virtual environment (especially the blue and red lines are at times
314 above and at times below the black line in panels B and C). To focus on the effects of adaptors, SD
315 data were again rearranged such that each lower panel in Fig. 3 shows the corresponding data from
316 the upper panel plotted re. baseline and combined after mirroring them across the left-right
317 symmetric conditions (as in Fig. 2). In experiment 1 (Fig. 3A), considering targets at 11° - 33° , the
318 ipsilateral and frontal adaptors induced an increased SD (approx. 0.5° ; red, magenta and, green
319 lines), while the contralateral adaptors had no effect (blue and cyan). Confirming this, an ANOVA
320 with the factors of adaptor ($-90^\circ, -45^\circ, 0^\circ, 45^\circ, 90^\circ$) and target ($11^\circ, 22^\circ, 33^\circ$) only found a
321 significant main effect of adaptor ($F(4, 28)=5.74, p=0.0017$). Post-hoc Bonferroni-corrected
322 pairwise comparisons are shown in the table inset in Fig. 3A, which indicates by asterisks the
323 adaptor pairs significantly differing from each other. Based on this, the adaptors can be divided into
324 two groups, the $0^\circ, 45^\circ$, and 90° adaptors (green, red, and magenta) and the -45° and -90° adaptors
325 (blue and cyan) such that the pairwise differences are significant for all adaptor pairs between the
326 groups and for none within the groups. Note that the factor of target was not significant, suggesting
327 that the effects were approximately equal across the three targets within a hemisphere.

328 In experiment 2 (Fig. 3B and 3C) the effect of adaptor on SDs was very different compared to
329 experiment 1, while being similar between the two virtual environments. The lateral adaptor (red
330 line) caused an increase in SDs for the nearest target (30°) as well as for the most distant target ($-$
331 30°), while it caused a decrease in SD for intermediate targets at 10° to 20° . This effect was much
332 stronger in the virtual anechoic environment (difference of 2° in panel C) than in the virtual

333 reverberant environment (difference of 1° in panel B). For the frontal adaptor (green line), there was
 334 a similar very weak trend, with the SD slightly positive for the nearest 10° target and slightly negative
 335 for the most distant 30° target. Confirming these observations, an ANOVA with the factors of
 336 environment (reverberant, anechoic), adaptor (-50°, 0°, 50°), and target (10°, 20°, 30°) found a
 337 significant adaptor x target interaction ($F(4,32)=3.63, p=0.037$). Partial ANOVAs performed
 338 separately for each adaptor only found a significant effect of target for the adaptor at +50° ($F(2,$
 339 $16)=4.68, p=0.028$), with post-hoc t-tests finding a significant difference between the 30° and 10°
 340 target and the 30° and 20° target.

341

352 FIG. 3 Upper panels show mean standard deviation (SD) in responses (\pm SEM) in target trials in
 353 experiment 1 (panel A) and experiment 2 (panels B and C), plotted as a function of target location
 354 separately for each adaptor condition (including no-adaptor baseline). For each panel in the upper
 355 row, a panel in the lower row shows the SD (\pm SEM) in responses to each adaptor re. no-adaptor
 356 baseline after mirroring the data, the effects are left-right symmetric. Thick lines highlight the subset

357 of data points that are independent after the mirroring. Inset in panel A is a table showing results of
358 post-hoc t-test pairwise comparisons between SDs for different adaptors (indicated by the color of
359 the corresponding line), with asterisks representing significance level of $p < 0.05$ (see text for details).

360 *2. Discussion*

361 In the real environment of experiment 1, both the 45° and 90° lateral adaptors had a similar
362 effect, inducing an increase in SDs for the ipsilateral but not for the contralateral targets. Similarly,
363 the 0° adaptor caused an increase in SDs for all the targets. These results are similar to the real room
364 results of Kopčo et al. (2007), again supporting the main hypothesis that passive listening is
365 sufficient to induce CP. Considering the proposed mechanisms of CP, the result is consistent with
366 the mechanism causing a suppression in neural activation after adaptation which then results in
367 noisier responses (Carlile et al., 2001), not with the mechanism where adaptation serves to increase
368 separability of targets, which would predict a reduced SD (Lingner et al., 2018). However, similar to
369 the bias results, it is not clear why the effect of the 45° adaptor is not stronger than that of the 90°
370 adaptor, even though it is much closer to the targets.

371 In both virtual environments of experiment 2, the lateral adaptor induced an increased SD for
372 the nearest targets and reduced SD for the more distant ipsilateral targets. While the decreased SD
373 provides partial support for the Lingner et al. model of spatial adaptation, which would predict such
374 a reduction for all targets near the adaptor, the overall pattern is not in line with their suggestion that
375 spatial hearing adapts in order to improve separability since the SD actually increased for the targets
376 nearest to the adaptor. Instead, the current results support the alternative suggestion that the
377 subjects changed their strategy when localizing sounds in the virtual environment, as proposed
378 earlier in the discussion of biases. Specifically, if the subjects started to respond relative to the
379 known location of the adaptor which they used as an anchor, then it is possible that, for the
380 intermediate targets, they can respond more consistently (even if with a larger bias) than when

381 responding based on the absolute percept of the target location. And the increased SD for the
382 targets nearest to the adaptor might suggest that the suppression mechanism of Carlile et al.
383 dominates performance even if the response strategy has changed from absolute to relative.

384 Finally, baseline SDs were smaller in real than virtual environments. This is expected since
385 virtual simulation has limited accuracy, especially when non-individualized BRIRs are used (Carlile,
386 1996). However, the real SDs were even considerably lower than the 10° SDs observed in the
387 reverberant condition of Kopčo et al. (2007). This decrease is most likely due to a more accurate
388 response method used here (pointer and closed eyes in Kopčo et al. (2007), vs. keyboard input in the
389 current study), as shown in Kopčo et al. (2015).

390 Comparing virtual anechoic vs. reverberant SDs in current experiment 2 showed that virtual
391 anechoic SDs were larger. In contrast, Kopčo et al. (2007) found anechoic SDs to be lower than
392 reverberant SDs in real environments, consistent with the anechoic binaural cues being less distorted
393 than the reverberant ones (Shinn-Cunningham et al., 2005). It is likely that the larger degradation in
394 virtual anechoic environment is caused by the subjects being more sensitive to the quality of
395 simulation when fewer cues are available, like in the current anechoic HRTFs (which do not include
396 informative early reflections from floor or ceiling), possibly even losing their ability to externalize the
397 simulated sources (Best et al., 2020).

398 **C. Correlation Coefficient and Information Transfer Rate vs. Standard Deviation**

399 One of the main results of the response SD analysis was that it found some support for the
400 hypothesis that the effect of adaptor is to increase spatial separability (Lingner et al., 2018),
401 particularly in virtual anechoic space. To more directly evaluate this hypothesis, we next examined
402 two additional performance measures, Pearson correlation coefficient and the ITR, which consider
403 not only the spread of responses, but also their means.

404 Figure 4 shows these performance measures for experiments 1 (column A) and 2 (column B and
405 C, respectively, for the virtual reverberant and anechoic environments). The values were computed
406 across the independent target triplets (e.g., the positive azimuths shown by thick lines in Figs. 2 and
407 3) and considering only the lateral adaptors for which it is clearly defined which adaptor is near (i.e.,
408 ipsilateral to the target triplet) vs. far (i.e., contralateral). The upper panels in Fig. 4 show results for
409 SDs, obtained by simply averaging the data from Fig. 3 across the target triplets. The middle row
410 shows the correlations between actual and response target locations computed across the three
411 targets, while the bottom row shows the corresponding ITRs. Note that higher SD values
412 correspond to lower discriminability, while for the other two measures higher values correspond to
413 better performance.

414 In experiment 1, performance was better with contralateral than ipsilateral adaptor for all three
415 performance measures (blue and cyan are better than red and magenta). ANOVAs with the factors
416 of adaptor absolute azimuth (45° , 90°) and adaptor laterality (ipsi, contra) only found a significant
417 main effect of laterality (SDs: $F(1,7)=16.02$, $p=0.0052$; CC: $F(1,7)=5.80$, $p=0.0046$; ITR:
418 $F(1,7)=6.33$, $p=0.04$).

419 In experiment 2, there was no significant effect of laterality on SDs or CCs. On the other hand,
420 the contralateral performance was always better in terms of ITR (blue is above red in the bottom
421 row of panels B and C). Finally, in the ITR and CC measures the virtual anechoic performance was
422 worse than virtual reverberant performance, which was worse than the real reverberant
423 performance. Confirming these observations, ANOVAs with the factors of adaptor laterality (ipsi,
424 contra) and environment (virtual anechoic, virtual reverberant) performed separately on the three
425 measures only found a significant effect of adaptor laterality for ITR ($F(1,8)=5.38$, $p=0.049$) while
426 the effect of environment was significant for ITR and correlation measures [CC: $F(1,8)=29.83$,
427 $p=0.0006$; ITR: $F(1,8)=5.69$, $p=0.044$], but not for SDs [$F(1,8)=3.06$, $p=0.12$].

428

429 FIG. 4 The effect of ipsilateral and contralateral adaptors on the overall performance evaluated by
 430 three different measures (rows) across a triplet of targets at 11° to 33° in experiments 1 and 2
 431 (columns). Upper row: mean of standard deviations across 3 target locations (10°, 20°, 30°)/(11°,
 432 22°, 33°) from Fig. 3. Middle row: Correlation coefficients between subject's responses and actual
 433 target locations. Lower row: Values of Information Transfer Rate for the triplets of targets. Asterisks
 434 indicate significant difference based on ANOVA ($p < 0.05$).

435 **3. Discussion**

436 These results, in particular those based on ITR, are consistent with the notion that source
 437 location discriminability is decreased near the adaptor, as would be predicted by the Carlile et al.
 438 (2001) model, and contrary to the increased discriminability predicted by the Lingner et al. (2018)

439 model. Importantly, Lingner et al. (2018) study was performed in virtual anechoic environment, the
440 same environment in which a decreased SD was observed for targets 20-30° away from adaptor in
441 the current study (Fig. 3). Also, a similar study by Getzmann (2004) found increased discriminability
442 near adaptor in a real anechoic environment. Thus, it might be that in anechoic environment the
443 subjects might improve their discriminability for specific targets, e.g. as a consequence of changing
444 their response strategy particularly in anechoic environments, and using relative localization
445 anchored at the known adaptor location when responding to the target.

446 Overall, only the ITR measure appears to be sufficiently robust and insensitive to possible non-
447 linearities in the stimulus-response mapping to show a significant support for the Carlile et al. (2001)
448 model in all the environments examined here. Also, when comparing performance across the
449 environments, only ITR and correlation confirm the result that performance in the real reverberant
450 environment is the best while in the virtual anechoic environment it is the worst. Thus, SD appears
451 to be the least sensitive measure of discriminability based on localization tasks.

452 **D. Temporal Profile of Contextual Plasticity**

453 Figure 5 plots the temporal profile of CP as a function of subrun within experimental runs.
454 Here, one subrun is defined as a group of trials in which each of the six targets was presented exactly
455 once (note that the target presentation order was pseudo-random such that each target was
456 presented at least once before any target was presented for a second time). The vertical dotted lines
457 separate the pre-/post-adaptation subruns containing only target trials from the adaptation subruns
458 in which adaptor trials and target trials were interleaved. Since the magnitude of the induced biases
459 was similar across the 3 unique targets (10°, 20° and 30°, as shown by the thick lines in the lower
460 panels of Fig. 2), the temporal analysis was performed on data averaged across these targets. The
461 upper panels of Fig. 5 show the bias re. actual target location in the no-adaptor baseline runs, while
462 the lower panels show the bias in the individual adaptor runs re. the baseline from the respective

463 upper panel. The columns again represent the three different environments examined in the two
 464 experiments.
 465

466 FIG. 5 Temporal profile of CP for the baseline runs (upper row) and adaptor runs (lower row) in
 467 experiment 1 (panel A) and experiment 2 (panels B and C). Across-subject mean biases (\pm SEM) re.
 468 actual location (upper row) or re. baseline (lower row) is plotted as a function of subrun within a
 469 run, averaged across the 3 unique target locations (10° - 30°) after combining the left-right
 470 symmetrical data. Pre-adaptation and post-adaptation subruns are separated from the adaptation
 471 subruns by dotted vertical lines.

472 The upper panels show that there were no strong drifts in the baseline runs, with offsets across
 473 different panels corresponding to the pattern of overshooting and undershooting observed across
 474 the experiments in Fig. 2. The lower panels show strong buildup for the ipsilateral adaptors ($45^\circ/50^\circ$
 475 and 90° , red and magenta lines), while the buildup in the remaining adaptor conditions (green, blue

476 and cyan lines) was relatively weak and noisy, making it difficult to estimate specific characteristics of
477 the buildup. Therefore, and since the 90° adaptor had a buildup similar to the 45° adaptor in
478 experiment 1 (magenta vs. red in panel A), this analysis focused on the ipsilateral adaptors at
479 45°/50° (red lines). The individual data from both experiments were fitted parametrically using first-
480 order exponential function (Andrejková et al., 2023), yielding time constant τ for the adaptation to
481 the context (data of one subject from experiment 1 was excluded as the fitting did not converge). In
482 experiment 1, the buildup was relatively slow ($\tau = 2$ subruns, red line in panel A), while in
483 experiment 2 it was faster in anechoic environment ($\tau=0.93$ subrun, panel C), with the reverberant
484 value falling between the other two ($\tau=1.39$ subrun, panel B). T-tests performed on the τ values only
485 found a significant difference between the real reverberant and virtual anechoic environments
486 ($t(14)=2.45$; $p=0.028$). Finally, in the post-adaptation (subruns 17-19) the effect started to weaken,
487 decreasing to approximately a half of the adaptation peak reached at the end of adaptation in all
488 three environments.

489 **4. Discussion**

490 The main result of this analysis, that the buildup of CP is faster in the virtual anechoic than in
491 real reverberant space, is consistent with the real environment results of Andrejková et al. (2023). As
492 suggested there, if the mechanism driving CP is dependent on the overall stimulus distribution, then
493 the anechoic-vs-reverberant difference might be caused by reverberation being omnidirectional,
494 making the distribution of arriving sounds more uniform than in the anechoic environment.
495 Specifically, assuming that CP is sensitive to the stimulus distribution mean, that mean is shifted off
496 the midline for the lateral adaptors. However, because of the omnidirectionality of reverberation, the
497 extent of that shift is reduced in reverberation, providing an explanation for why the buildup of CP
498 might be slower, and weaker, in reverberation.

499 An alternative, or additional, factor explaining the difference might be that in the virtual
500 environments, the listeners tend to use more relative response strategy, comparing the target
501 location to the known adaptor location, while in the real environment they use more direct absolute
502 target location estimation (as suggested in the preceding sections). Such a switch in response strategy
503 might occur immediately after the first adaptor presentation, explaining the abrupt onset of CP
504 particularly in the virtual anechoic environment. To further evaluate this hypothesis, we re-analyzed
505 the response biases in the adaptation subruns (shown in Fig. 2) after splitting the data by whether
506 the preceding trial was an adaptor trial or a target trial. This analysis found no effect of the preceding
507 trial type in the real reverberant environment of experiment 1, while the bias was larger immediately
508 after the adaptor trial than after a target trial in experiment 2. Specifically, for the targets near the
509 lateral adaptor, the difference was approximately 2° in virtual reverberant and 6° in virtual anechoic
510 environments (data not shown). Thus, not only at the beginning of the adaptation, but throughout
511 the adaptation portion of each run, responses shifted more away from the adaptor immediately after
512 the adaptor presentation in virtual environments, but not in the real environment. This result
513 supports the idea that in the virtual environments the subjects responded relatively to the adaptor
514 location, and that they consistently overestimated the contrast from it to the target.

515 Finally, the biases induced during adaptation persisted during the three post-adaptation subruns
516 in all the environments, confirming that the relatively slow adaptation component of CP persists at
517 least over tens of seconds when the adaptor stops being presented, consistent with the time scale
518 previously reported for frontal sources in real environments (Hládek et al., 2017). Importantly, since
519 the relative strategy-switching component in virtual environments likely did not affect the post-
520 adaptation performance (as there was no adaptor to be used as an anchor anymore), these results
521 confirm that there is a slow component of CP that has a comparable temporal profile in real and
522 virtual environments.

523 IV. GENERAL DISCUSSION

524 The current study primarily examined two questions about contextual plasticity: 1) whether it
525 can be induced by passive listening to adaptors, and 2) whether it can also be observed in virtual
526 environments. Experiment 1, performed in a real reverberant environment, found that passive
527 listening is sufficient to induce both response biases and increased response SDs for targets near the
528 adaptor (Fig. 2 and 3, respectively). Experiment 2, performed in virtual environments, found 1) that
529 some of the induced biases were larger than in the real environment while the response SDs could
530 either increase or decrease near the adaptor, and 2) that these effects were stronger in the anechoic
531 than the reverberant virtual environment. Consistent across all the environments, overall
532 performance expressed as ITR was always worse near the adaptor than far from the adaptor (Fig. 4).
533 Finally, the buildup of adaptation was faster in the virtual anechoic than the real reverberant
534 environment, with virtual reverberant environment performance falling in between (Fig. 5).

535 The mechanism underlying contextual plasticity is largely unknown. The current study showed
536 that active responding during adaptation is not necessary to induce CP, supporting the hypothesis
537 that it is caused by passive adaptation in some neural spatial representation whose mechanism is
538 similar to the localization aftereffect (Andrejková et al., 2023). Specifically, it is likely to be driven by
539 changes in the stimulus distribution (Andrejková et al., 2023; Dahmen et al., 2010; Laback, 2023),
540 e.g., by changing the operating point of the neural channels (Dahmen et al., 2010) or by fatiguing of
541 spatial channels due to repeated presentation of the adaptor (Carlile et al., 2001). However, it is still
542 possible that some aspects of active localization on adaptation trials do influence CP, as the current
543 experiment differed from the previous CP studies (e.g., Hládek et al., 2017) also in other ways, not
544 only by the passive listening on the adaptation trials. To determine the contribution of active
545 listening to CP, future studies could directly compare active and passive listening using an otherwise
546 identical setup.

547 The current study examined CP in new spatial configurations. First, it used midline-symmetric
548 target locations of -33° to 33° , which minimized temporal drifts in the no-adaptor baseline, as
549 observed previously (Andrejková et al., 2023). Second, the adaptor locations were not only at the
550 edge of the target range (45°) as in the previous studies, but also in the middle (0°) or at the extreme
551 azimuth of 90° (only in experiment 1). Considering the 45° and 90° adaptors, if the CP induced by
552 them had similar strength and simply decreased with azimuth, the CP induced by the 45° adaptor
553 was expected to be much stronger than that induced by the more distant 90° adaptor. Contrary to
554 this expectation, the effects of the 45° and 90° adaptor were comparable in terms of both response
555 bias and response SD, with both measures decreasing for targets further away from the adaptors.
556 This result suggests that either the effect is induced in a hemispheric representation not sensitive to
557 the specific adaptor location within the hemisphere (McAlpine et al., 2016), or that the 90° adaptor
558 induces a much stronger and broader effect than the 45° adaptor. It is also worth noting that the
559 effects observed here, particularly in terms of SD, might have been stronger if they were measured
560 also for targets at the adaptor locations, as previously observed in discrimination studies (e.g.,
561 Getzmann, 2004).

562 While the lateral adaptor results are consistent with previous CP studies at least in that the effect
563 strength decreases with adaptor-target separation, the current 0° results do not follow this pattern, as
564 1) both the biases and SDs are approximately constant across all target locations and 2) the CP
565 induced by this adaptor was much weaker here than in a comparable condition of Hládek et al.
566 (2017). It is likely that both these differences are driven by the change in the spatial arrangement in
567 the current study in which the 0° adaptor was located in the middle of the target range (the adaptor
568 was always on the edge of the target range in Hládek et al. (2017), and other previous studies). This
569 result supports the suggestion that the distribution of all the stimuli including the targets, not only
570 the distribution of adaptors, needs to be considered when determining the size and direction of the

571 CP biases (Andrejková et al., 2023). However, Andrejková et al. (2023) evaluated the stimulus
572 distribution mean as the statistic predicting the induced bias. Here, the 0° adaptor condition had the
573 same mean as the baseline condition and no adaptation would be predicted based on the distribution
574 mean statistic. Since an expansion of the spatial representation around the adaptor was observed,
575 other distribution statistics, e.g., its standard deviation (Laback, 2023) might need to be considered.
576 Importantly, this result is challenging even for the hemispheric models of auditory spatial
577 representation (Braasch, 2015; Encke and Dietz, 2022; Lingner et al., 2018; McAlpine et al., 2016) as
578 both channels are adapted equally by a central adaptor. Therefore, as a minimum, a third central
579 channel is required to predict the expansion of spatial representation (Dingle et al., 2012).

580 In the virtual environment, the CP effects pattern was similar to that in the real environment,
581 with two notable differences. First, while the effect of the frontal adaptor was comparable in terms
582 of both biases and SDs, the effect of lateral adaptors was much larger in terms of bias (up to 16° in
583 virtual vs. 5° in real environment) and more complex in terms of SDs (increase in real environment
584 vs. increase followed by decrease in virtual environment). Second, the buildup of adaptation was
585 faster in the virtual environment, especially the anechoic one, in which it had a very transient
586 component that grew after every adaptor trial and disappeared after every target trial. These
587 differences are most likely driven by a much larger uncertainty about how to map the acoustic cues
588 to the physical sources in the virtual environment, as indicated by the increase in the baseline
589 response SDs in virtual environments (5° to 6° vs. 3° in real reverberant environment). It is likely
590 that the subjects use the adaptor, presented from a known location, as an anchor and combine the
591 relative information about the target location re. the recently heard adaptor with a direct absolute
592 estimation of the target location based on its ITD and ILD (Kopčo et al., 2010). Assuming that this
593 relative location gets overestimated for the lateral adaptors, possibly because the subjects know on
594 which side of the adaptor to expect the targets, this mechanism can explain the increased biases as

595 well as the reduced SDs for targets at some locations (e.g., if it is assumed that the relative location
596 estimation is combined with the absolute estimation, resulting in a more stable percept). This
597 mechanism also provides an alternative explanation to the previous adaptation studies which
598 reported increased location discriminability near the adaptor (Getzmann, 2004; Lingner et al., 2018).
599 Specifically, it proposes that the improved discriminability is due to relative response strategy which
600 subjects might use especially in anechoic environment (virtual or real, in which the previous studies
601 were performed). However, note that relative response strategy is in fact required in discrimination
602 studies, thus responding relative to the adaptor might be a more natural strategy there.

603 To more directly evaluate the proposal by Lingner et al. (2018) that the adaptation is the
604 consequence of the system being tuned to separating sources as opposed to accurately localizing
605 them, the current study evaluated the localization performance using two additional measures: the
606 correlation coefficient and the information transfer rate. Both of these measures have the property
607 that they do not penalize constant biases in responses, thus providing information about how
608 discriminable the sources would be in a discrimination experiment based on localization
609 performance. Contrary to the Lingner et al. proposal, both of these measures (and, in particular, the
610 ITR) show that performance was worse near the adaptors in all three environments examined here,
611 supporting the alternative hypothesis that the adaptation results from fatiguing or suppressing
612 certain spatial channels in the auditory representation (Carlile et al., 2001; Dingle et al., 2012;
613 Thurlow and Jack, 1973).

614 The current study is, to our knowledge, the first one to introduce the ITR as an overall
615 localization performance measure that is robust against constant biases as well as non-linearities in
616 the stimulus-response mapping. It is shown here that it is more sensitive than CC when evaluating
617 the effect of adaptor on targets near and far from it and it is likely it can be considered as an overall
618 measure of discriminability of stimuli in a localization study or when multiple sources are to be

619 discriminated. Using the ITR, the current study found overall performance to be the best in real
620 reverberant environment, intermediate in the virtual reverberant environment and worst in the
621 virtual anechoic environment (a result that was confirmed also when CC was considered). While the
622 degradation in virtual environments compared to real environments is expected, the lower
623 performance in virtual anechoic compared to virtual reverberant environment is counterintuitive, as
624 in real environments reverberation typically causes degradation in horizontal localization (Devore
625 and Delgutte, 2010; Giguere and Abel, 1993; Hartmann, 1983; Kopčo et al., 2007; Rakerd and
626 Hartmann, 1985, 2004). At least two factors might drive this effect. First, reverberation causes the
627 simulation to be more naturalistic as the reflections arrive from all directions, not only the discrete
628 target locations, improving externalization and mapping from the binaural cues to the horizontal
629 location (Best et al., 2020). Second, some of the reverberant energy provides additional horizontal
630 information, as, in particular, the first reflection typically coming from the floor or the ceiling, has
631 the same azimuthal direction as the direct sound (Shinn-Cunningham et al., 2005).

632 In summary, the current study advanced our understanding of CP by showing that the effect can
633 be induced by passive listening, and that it can be stronger in virtual than in real environments.
634 These results support the suggestion that CP is related to the localization aftereffect (or, more
635 generally, the precursor effect; Laback, 2023; Lingner et al., 2018; Phillips and Hall, 2005). However,
636 it differs from those effects in that it is induced by very short stimuli and builds up on a slower time
637 scale of tens of seconds to minutes (in the current study, the separation between adaptor and target
638 trials was on average approximately 5 seconds). Moreover, based on the current results, it cannot be
639 excluded that active listening also contributes to CP (e.g., that the effect is stronger when the
640 listeners have to localize a target presented immediately after the adaptor, as in the previous CP
641 studies) or that it is also partially due to the listeners modifying their localization strategy (e.g., from
642 absolute to relative) in presence of the adaptor (Hládek et al., 2017). Additionally, the current results

643 are important for the general understanding of the mechanisms of horizontal sound localization and
644 its adaptation, as similar slow adaptive effects might have influenced also the results of other studies
645 that did not consider them. For example, a binaural trading ratio study of Moore et al. (2020)
646 considered the effect of an immediately preceding adaptor but not of possible slower adaptation to a
647 cue that was fixed throughout a block of trials. Similarly, the Getzman et al. (2004) study mentioned
648 above considered the effect of immediately preceding adaptor but kept that adaptor fixed
649 throughout a block. More generally, many everyday listening situations might cause such slow
650 adaptative effects. For example, consider a listener following – and adapting to – a static talker and
651 then trying to localize an unexpected sound from a new location. Finally, multiple response
652 measures have been proposed to evaluate sound localization accuracy (Culling and Summerfield,
653 1998). Here, we introduced ITR as a measure that evaluates overall separability between individual
654 target locations while not penalizing for any non-linearities or biases in the stimulus-response
655 mapping.

656

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660

661 **AUTHOR DECLARATIONS**

662 **Conflict of Interest**

663 The authors have no conflicts to disclose.

664 **Ethics Approval**

665 The current study was approved by the Ethical Review Authority of P. J. Šafárik University in
666 Košice.

667 **DATA AVAILABILITY**

668 The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author
669 upon reasonable request.

670
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